

Protonation equilibria of glycyglycine and histamine in cationic micellar media

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Abstract : Solute-solvent interactions of glycyglycine and histamine has been studied in various concentrations (0.5–2.5% w/v) of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) solution maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ at 303 K. The protonation constants have been calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75 and the best fit models are arrived at based on statistical grounds employing crystallographic *R* factor, χ^2 , skewness and kurtosis. These protonation constants values have been found to shift in micellar media as compared to those in pure water. The differences in the values have been attributed to the solvent properties of the interfacial and bulk phases involving contribution from the micellar surface potential in the case of charged micelles. The trend of log values of step-wise protonation constants with mole fraction of the medium have been explained based on electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces operating on the protonation equilibria. Distributions of species, protonation equilibria and effect of influential parameters on the protonation constants have also been presented.

Keywords : Protonation equilibria, MINQUAD75, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, glycyglycine, histamine.

Introduction

Peptides are an amazing class of compounds constructed from relatively simple building blocks, the amino acids. They are components of tissues¹ exhibiting a remarkable range of biological properties acting as antibiotics, hormones, food additives, poisons or pain-killers². Several metal complexes containing peptide groups have displayed diverse pharmacological activities. For instance, copper complexes with amino acids and peptides as ligands show anti-inflammatory and cytostatic activities^{3,4}. Investigations involving the peptides in acid-base reactions^{5–7} particularly, small peptides have attracted great attention in relation to the chemistry because these compounds are usually considered as good model systems to attain a better insight into the characteristics of naturally occurring metalloproteins^{8–10}. Vast data are available on the protonation and stability constants of the amino acids and simple peptides in water and organic solvents^{11–19}. However, the protonation constants of amino acids and peptides in

these organic solvents are often different from those in water, as these media tend to be lipophilic rather than hydrophilic^{20,21}. Little is known about the chemistry of amino acids and simple peptides in mixed solvents, in regard to their protonation constants²² and experiments shown that one solvent alone is not an ideal model for *in vivo* reactions²³.

Glycyglycine (GG) is the simplest dipeptide made from the residues of two glycine molecules. The transition of dipeptide from the molecular form to the zwitterions form does not depend on the acidity of the medium. Glycyglycine is a potentially useful zwitterionic buffer in the physiological pH range (6.0–8.5)²⁴.

Histamine, a biological amine, was synthesized in 1907 and characterized in 1910 as a substance (“beta-1”) ²⁵, is considered as a principle mediator of many pathological processes regulating several essential events in allergies and autoimmune diseases. Niemann and Hays, based mainly on the histamine-like activity of β -(2-pyridyl)-

ethylamine proposed that the biological activity of histamine depends on the existence of an intramolecular H bond between the protonated amino group and the "pyridine" nitrogen of the imidazole ring²⁶. This hypothesis was strengthened by Lee and Jones²⁷ analysis of the structural requirements for histamine-like activity in a number of compounds.

Histamine exhibits two main important basic functionalities such as primary aliphatic amine (pK_{a1} 9.4) and imidazole (pK_{a2} 5.8). These make the monocation with different tautomers; the preferred form at physiologic pH value (96%) with a minor dicationic fraction (3%) and a very small amount of the neutral form²⁸. Basing on this several workers were reported protonation constant studies on histamine²⁹.

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) is a cationic surfactant which tends to denature proteins and profoundly influences the bulk properties of physiological systems. They can solubilise, concentrate and compartmentalize ions and molecules³⁰. Cationic micellar media can shift acid-base equilibria. This shift can be explained in terms of differences between the properties of the bulk solvent and of the interfacial region and perturbation of the acid-base equilibria by the electrostatic field effect of the charged interface. The dissociation equilibria of substituted benzoic acids in cationic and anionic micelles have been investigated potentiometrically³¹. It was shown that their pK_a values shift to about 0.5–3.0 in anionic micelles. The acid-base equilibria of a number of phenols, amines and carboxylic acids in aqueous micellar solutions have been examined³². The present work is an attempt to study the impact of cationic micellar solution on the dissociation equilibria of glycylglycine and histamine.

Experimental

Chemicals and standard solutions :

All the chemicals used in this investigation were of analytical reagent grade purity. Solutions of 0.05 M glycylglycine (Hi-media), 0.05 M histamine (Spectrochem), 0.2 M hydrochloric acid (Merck, India), 0.4 M sodium hydroxide (Merck, India) and 2.0 M sodium chloride (Merck, India) were prepared. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Triple-distilled deionized water was used for preparation of all the solutions. The acid and

base solutions were standardized by standard methods. The concentration of the alkali was determined by titrating it with standard oxalic acid and potassium hydrogen phthalate solutions, while the normality of hydrochloric acid was determined using the standardized sodium hydroxide and the primary standard borax solutions. So as to assess the errors that might have crept into the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA) using the computer program COST³³. The strength of the prepared carbonate-free sodium hydroxide solution was determined by titrating it against hydrochloric acid solution using the Gran plot method³⁴.

Instrumentation and analytical procedures :

The pH measurements of proton-ligand system were carried out in aqueous media containing varying compositions of surfactant CTAB in the range of 0.5–2.5% w/v maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 M with sodium chloride at 303.0 ± 0.1 K using a 905 Autotitrando Analyzer (Metrohm, Switzerland) type (readability 0.001). Potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 M) and borax (0.01 M) solutions were used to calibrate the Autotitrando Analyzer. In each titration, the titrand consisted approximately 1 mmol of hydrochloric acid. The amounts of the glycylglycine, histamine (ligands) in the titrand are in the range of 0.25 to 0.50 mmol. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred surfactant-water mixture containing inert electrolyte for several days. At regular intervals, the strong acid was titrated against alkali to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. The details of experimental procedure and titration assembly used in our laboratory have been given elsewhere³⁵.

Modeling strategy :

The approximate protonation constants of glycylglycine and histamine were calculated with the computer program SCPHD^{36–38}. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares computer program, MINQUAD75³⁹, which exploit the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. The variation of stepwise protonation constants ($\log K$) with the mole fraction of the medium was analyzed on electrostatic grounds for the solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The best fit models containing the type of species and overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. A very low standard deviation (SD) in $\log \beta$ values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom indicate that the experimental data can be represented by the model. The small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around zero mean with little dispersion.

The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic pattern in the case of both glycylglycine and histamine. The values of kurtosis given in Table 1. The values of skewness recorded in Table 1 are between -0.86 and 2.57 . These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, least squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R -values. These statistical parameters thus show that the best fit models portray the acido-basic equilibria of glycylglycine and histamine in CTAB-water mixtures. Alkali metric titration data are simulated using the model parameters given in Table 1. These data are com-

pared with the experimental alkalimetric titration data, to verify the sufficiency of the models. The overlap of the typical experimental and simulated titrations data given in Fig. 1 indicates that the proposed models represent the experimental data.

Secondary formation functions :

Secondary formation functions like average number of protons bound per mole of ligand (\bar{n}_{H}) and number of moles of alkali consumed per mole of ligand (**a**) are useful to detect the number of equilibria. Plots of \bar{n}_{H} versus pH for different concentrations of the ligand should overlap if there is no formation of polymeric species. Overlapping formation curves for glycylglycine and histamine (Fig. 2) rule out the polymerization of the ligand molecules. The pH values at half integral values of \bar{n}_{H} correspond to the protonation constants of the ligands. Two half integrals (1.5 and 0.5) in the case of glycylglycine (Fig. 2(A)) and two half integral (1.5 and 0.5) in the case of histamine (Fig. 2(B)) emphasize the presence of three and one protonation-deprotonation equilibria in the pH range of present study. The number of plateaus in the formation curves corresponds to the number of these equilibria.

The plots of **a** versus pH are given in Fig. 3. The negative values of **a** correspond to the number of moles of free acid present in the titrand and the number of associable

Table 1. Best fit chemical models of acido-basic equilibria of glycylglycine and histamine in CTAB-water mixtures
Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

% w/v of CTAB	$\log \beta_1(\text{SD})$	$\log \beta_2(\text{SD})$	NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	R -factor	pH range
Glycylglycine									
0	8.15(2)	11.51(3)	32	3.33	0.03	2.00	9.50	0.0168	2.1–10.0
0.5	7.86(2)	11.16(4)	73	1.24	0.49	3.44	5.56	0.0241	2.2–9.8
1.0	8.00(3)	11.34(6)	52	2.09	2.57	10.31	16.46	0.0334	3.2–10.9
1.5	8.18(3)	11.26(7)	56	4.38	-0.35	3.06	1.29	0.0283	2.3–9.00
2.0	7.90(3)	11.01(6)	69	3.14	-0.28	3.19	5.88	0.0319	2.3–10.0
2.5	8.17(4)	11.32(7)	53	3.52	-0.37	3.75	2.98	0.0353	2.3–9.50
Histamine									
0	9.72(4)	15.40(8)	61	7.45	-0.68	5.03	20.4	0.0025	3.9–11.2
0.5	9.82(2)	15.90(4)	64	1.49	-0.18	3.29	3.13	0.0327	3.2–10.9
1.0	9.73(4)	15.61(7)	61	4.45	-0.66	2.83	1.54	0.0317	3.2–10.8
1.5	9.87(3)	15.83(6)	59	2.05	-0.63	3.09	6.47	0.0286	3.2–10.9
2.0	10.02(4)	15.91(6)	52	4.58	-0.86	3.52	9.69	0.0261	3.2–10.8
2.5	10.12(4)	16.19(5)	62	3.71	0.01	3.78	11.48	0.0353	2.9–10.9

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(\text{NP} - m) \times 10^8$; NP = Number of points; m = number of protonation constants; SD = standard deviation.

Fig. 1. Simulated (o) and experimental (solid line) alkali metric titration curves in 2.0% w/v CTAB-water mixtures, (A) glycylglycine, (B) histamine; (a) 0.25, (b) 0.375 and (c) 0.50 mmol, respectively.

Fig. 2. Plots of \bar{n}_H versus pH in 2.0% w/v CTAB-water mixture; (A) glycylglycine, (B) histamine; (Δ) 0.25, (O) 0.375 and (\square) 0.50 mmol, respectively.

Fig. 3. Variation of a with pH in 1.0% w/v CTAB-water mixture; (A) glycylglycine, (B) histamine, respectively.

protons. The positive values of a indicate the number of dissociable protons in the ligand molecules.

Distribution diagrams :

Typical distribution plots produced by DISPLOT⁴⁰⁻⁴³

using protonation constants from the best fit models are shown in Fig. 4. A single representative plot is shown for each system at a particular CTAB-water concentration. The zwitterion of glycylglycine, LH, is present to an ex-

Fig. 4. Species distribution diagrams of (A) glycyglycine, (B) histamine in 2.0% w/v CTAB-water mixtures.

tent of 98% in the pH range 2.5–9.0. The distribution plot of glycyglycine in Fig. 4(A) is shows the existence of LH_2^+ , L^- . In the case of histamine, LH^+ is present to an extent of 98.5% in the pH range 4.5–10.5. The distribution plot of histamine in Fig. 4(B) shows the existence of LH_2^{2+} , L . The corresponding protonation-deprotonation equilibria are shown in Fig. 5.

Effect of surfactant :

The above results show that the shifts in protonation

constant values are more in case of cationic surfactant CTAB. Both acids behave more strongly in CTAB whose interfacial layer is positively charged. This is mainly because the anion from acid molecule, $X^{(z-1)}$, is strongly attracted to the interfacial layer of the cationic surfactants due to attraction between opposite charges, coupled with its strong hydrophobic character. This creates a strain on the acid molecule. Hence the acid dissociates more strongly.

Many workers were of the opinion that both electro-

Fig. 5. Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of (A) glycyglycine, (B) histamine.

static and non-electrostatic effects should be considered even in the case of simple acido-basic equilibria; one dominates the other, depending upon the nature of solute and solvent^{44,45}. Born's classical treatment⁴⁶ holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. The number of micelles increases with the concentration of surfactant and oppositely charged ions are concentrated in the Stern layer. Fig. 6 shows the linear variation of the step-wise protonation constants of glycylglycine and histamine with the mole fraction of CTAB, may be because of the electrostatic interaction.

Micelles alter the reaction rates and shift equilibria primarily by concentrating reactants within the small volume of micellar pseudo phase. The extent of change is a product of the micellar effect on the reaction within the micellar pseudo phase and the distribution of reactants between the two phases. The effect of micelles on overall reaction rates and equilibria depends upon the incorporation of solutes into the micellar pseudo phase.

Effect of systematic errors in best fit model :

MINIQUAD75 does not have provision to study the

Fig. 6. Variation of stepwise protonation constant (log *K*) with mole fraction of CTAB in CTAB-water mixtures. (A) glycylglycine, (B) histamine; (■) log *K*₁, (●) log *K*₂.

effect of systematic errors in the influential parameters like the concentration of ingredients and electrode calibration on the magnitude of protonation constant. In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different experimental with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the concentration of alkali, mineral acids and the ligands. The results of a typical system given in Table 2 emphasize that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and mineral acid affects the protonation constants more than that of the ligand.

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the protonation constants in 2.0% (w/v) CTAB-water mixture

Ingredient	Error (%)	Glycylglycine		Histamine	
		log β ₁	log β ₂	log β ₁	log β ₂
Acid	0	7.90(3)	11.01(6)	10.02(4)	15.91(8)
	-5	7.61(3)	10.38(5)	9.52(6)	14.87(14)
	-2	7.79(3)	10.75(5)	9.82(5)	15.81(10)
	+2	8.02(4)	11.27(7)	10.20(4)	16.29(8)
Alkali	+5	8.22(5)	11.72(10)	10.47(5)	16.86(8)
	-5	8.28(5)	11.68(10)	10.43(5)	16.65(8)
	-2	8.05(3)	11.26(7)	10.18(4)	16.21(8)
	+2	7.77(3)	10.77(5)	9.85(5)	15.61(10)
Ligand	+5	7.57(4)	10.43(6)	9.59(6)	15.15(11)
	-5	7.84(4)	11.02(7)	10.08(6)	16.15(8)
	-2	7.88(4)	11.01(6)	10.04(5)	16.008(9)
	+2	7.93(3)	11.01(6)	9.99(5)	15.82(9)
Volume	+5	8.17(5)	11.32(8)	9.96(5)	15.68(10)
	-5	7.88(3)	11.03(6)	10.01(5)	15.91(9)
	-2	7.88(3)	11.02(6)	10.02(5)	15.91(9)
	+2	7.88(3)	11.01(6)	10.02(5)	15.91(9)
log <i>F</i>	+5	7.88(3)	11.00(6)	10.02(5)	15.91(9)
	-5	7.93(4)	11.09(6)	10.01(5)	15.91(9)
	-2	7.91(3)	11.03(6)	10.01(5)	15.51(6)
	+2	7.89(3)	11.00(5)	10.02(5)	15.91(6)
	+5	7.89(3)	10.98(6)	10.02(5)	15.91(9)

Conclusions

- (i) Glycylglycine has one dissociable proton and one amino group which can associate with a proton. Glycylglycine forms LH₂⁺ at low pH and gets deprotonated with the formation of LH, and L⁻ successively with increase in pH.
- (ii) Histamine has two dissociable protons. Histamine form LH₂²⁺ at low pH and gets deproto-

nated with the formation of LH^+ and L successively with increase in pH.

- (iii) Secondary formation functions – number of moles of alkali consumes per mole of the ligand and average number of moles of protons bound per mole of the ligand – are useful in detecting the number of protonation equilibria and in guessing the approximate protonation constants.
- (iv) The linear variation of log values of protonation constants of glycylglycine and histamine with increasing mole fraction of CTAB in CTAB-water mixtures indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces in the protonation-deprotonation equilibria.
- (v) The effect of systematic errors in the influential parameters shows that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and mineral acids will affect the protonation constants more than that of the ligand.

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